

Biomarker-Agnostic Detection of Ovarian Cancer from Blood Plasma Using a Machine Learning-Driven Electronic Nose

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Early-stage ovarian cancer (OC) detection remains a major clinical challenge due to the limitations of existing diagnostic methods, which often lack sufficient sensitivity, specificity, or practicality for routine screening. Here, this study introduces a biomarker-agnostic, machine learning-driven diagnostic platform based on a 32-element metal-oxide semiconductor electronic nose, designed to analyze total volatile organic compound emissions from blood plasma. Custom feature extraction algorithms and a sensor utility assessment technique enable the development of a robust, interpretable, and explainable ensemble boosting model, achieving 97.0% sensitivity and 97.0% specificity in distinguishing OC patients from healthy controls. Patient-level classification using a majority-vote strategy results in 100% diagnostic accuracy. Furthermore, the model's adaptability to related diagnostic tasks is demonstrated—accurate OC staging and differentiation between ovarian and endometrial cancers—using the same feature extraction and sensor evaluation framework. This approach offers a rapid, noninvasive, and affordable diagnostic solution with high throughput potential. Its strong performance and transferability highlight its promise as a versatile tool in oncological diagnostics, supporting earlier intervention and improved patient outcomes. By enhancing early detection and diagnosis capabilities, this intelligent electronic nose system could significantly advance global OC screening strategies and reduce disease burden.

and 206 956 deaths globally, with age-standardized rates (ASR) of 6.7 and 4.0 per 100 000 people, respectively.^[2] Alarming, projections suggest these numbers will rise to 503 800 cases and 351 200 deaths by 2050.^[3] Prognosis is strongly stage-dependent: while patients diagnosed at stage I have an average five-year survival rate of 93%, this decreases sharply to 31% for those diagnosed with distant spread, including stage IV OC.^[4] Late-stage diagnosis not only substantially elevates mortality risk but also exacerbates the associated economic and social burden, with Hutchinson et al. estimating approximately \$70 billion in OC-related costs across 11 countries.^[5] These statistics underscore the urgent need for accurate, accessible, and scalable early detection strategies suitable for population-level screening.

Current diagnostic methods—including proteomic detection of serum biomarkers (e.g., carbohydrate antigen 125 (CA-125) and human epididymis protein 4 (HE4)), various imaging techniques (e.g., computed tomography (CT), transvaginal ultrasound (TVU), and positron emission tomography (PET)) and invasive procedures (e.g., biopsy or ovarian needle aspiration)—present significant limitations.^[6–11] These approaches often lack sufficient sensitivity and specificity for early-stage detection, are costly and invasive, cause pain and discomfort, and depend heavily on expert interpretation. Even multiparameter approaches like the Risk of Ovarian Malignancy Algorithm (ROMA), which integrates CA-125, HE4,

1. Introduction

Ovarian cancer (OC) is one of the deadliest gynecologic malignancies, primarily due to its asymptomatic or vague early presentation, which often results in diagnosis at advanced stages.^[1] Hence its “silent killer” moniker. In 2022, the World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF) reported 324 603 new OC cases

tomography (PET)) and invasive procedures (e.g., biopsy or ovarian needle aspiration)—present significant limitations.^[6–11] These approaches often lack sufficient sensitivity and specificity for early-stage detection, are costly and invasive, cause pain and discomfort, and depend heavily on expert interpretation. Even multiparameter approaches like the Risk of Ovarian Malignancy Algorithm (ROMA), which integrates CA-125, HE4,

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and menopausal status, fail to achieve the performance required for effective population screening.^[12] Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have enhanced conventional diagnostic tools (e.g., by improving ultrasound-based assessments and integrating bioinformatics with clinical data), yet these methods remain limited by their reliance on existing biomarkers and imaging modalities. Consequently, a critical need persists for rapid, non-invasive or minimally invasive, and cost-effective solutions capable of detecting OC at its earliest and most treatable stages.^[13–16]

One promising frontier is the analysis of the complete set of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) generated by living organisms, known as the volatilome, using a biomarker-agnostic approach that enables early cancer detection without the need to identify specific biomarkers. These VOCs, present in blood, breath, urine, and other biological matrices, reflect disease-specific metabolic alterations, enabling discrimination between healthy and cancerous states.^[17–19] Instead of relying on the quantification of individual molecular targets, volatilome-based diagnostics leverage holistic emission profiles, allowing rapid pattern-based classification of disease states and providing a viable, affordable alternative to traditional biomarker-dependent methods.

Electronic noses (*e*-noses)—devices that mimic mammalian olfactory systems using crossreactive sensor arrays—are particularly suited for detecting total VOC patterns and thus offer a robust, biomarker-independent solution for cancer detection.^[20–22] When coupled with machine learning (ML) algorithms, these systems transform complex sensor data into precise diagnostic predictions.^[23] This combination enhances accuracy and represents a minimally invasive, scalable technology with the potential to transform cancer diagnostics in the future.

Previous studies have shown that VOCs in blood plasma differ significantly between OC patients and healthy individuals.^[24,25]

The pioneering applications of *e*-noses for OC detection were reported by Horvath and Chilo in 2009–2010.^[26,27] These seminal studies demonstrated that OC tissue samples exhibit distinctive odor signatures compared to healthy controls, achieving detection capabilities with 84.4% sensitivity and 86.8% specificity. Horvath et al. subsequently extended this approach to blood specimens, showing that plasma headspace VOCs differ between cancer patients and healthy individuals, facilitating sensor-based classification.^[28] Kybert et al. further validated this possibility using canine olfactory detection, gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS), and single-stranded DNA-functionalized single-walled carbon nanotubes (ssDNA-SWCNT) to differentiate blood plasma from OC patients and healthy controls.^[29] Independent studies also confirmed the effectiveness of canine olfactory discrimination for OC detection via blood plasma VOCs.^[30] Additional research has explored alternative blood-derived matrices, such as serum and whole blood with anticoagulants.^[31,32] Kim et al. demonstrated high-grade serous ovarian carcinoma detection in serum samples ($n = 269$, comprising 56 high-grade serous OC cases, 71 healthy controls, 56 other gynecologic disease cases, 61 nongynecologic disease cases, and 25 remission cases) using a nanosensor array of organic color centers (OCCs)-functionalized, ssDNA-encapsulated SWCNTs, paired with support vector machine (SVM) modeling, achieving 87.0% sensitivity and 98.0% specificity.^[31] In a mouse model study ($n = 157$, comprising 17 OC cases and 22 healthy controls),

a hybrid sensor array combining chemiresistors (gold nanoparticles capped with organic layers) and SWCNTs (capped with polymer composites), integrated with discriminant factor analysis (DFA), achieved 84.4% accuracy, 91.6% specificity, and 81.0% sensitivity.^[32] Amal et al.^[33] demonstrated that exhaled breath VOCs from 182 subjects (48 OC, 48 healthy controls, and 86 benign gynecologic neoplasia) reflect OC-associated metabolic alterations. Using a nanoarray of chemically modified gold nanoparticles and SWCNT networks, with analyzed via DFA, they achieved 79.0% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and 89.0% accuracy. A subsequent study using a metal-oxide semiconductor (MOS)-based *e*-nose and a K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm analyzed breath samples from 251 women (86 OC, 51 benign masses, 114 healthy controls), yielding 98.0% sensitivity and 95.0% specificity.^[34] Furthermore, combined *e*-nose and electronic tongue (*e*-tongue) technologies analyzed breath, urine, and blood from 93 patients (50 OC, 43 healthy controls) using partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA), achieving 86.0% sensitivity and 88.0% specificity.^[35] Collectively, these findings highlight the robustness and versatility of VOC-based diagnostic strategies across various biological matrices.

Despite these advances, existing classifiers distinguishing OC from healthy plasma samples remain limited in their ability to identify disease stages and often exhibit suboptimal performance in early-stage detection, where screening tests would have the greatest impact. Current models primarily detect the presence of OC as a general condition rather than quantifying disease progression. Moreover, most prior studies rely on small sample sizes (typically <100 OC cases) and *e*-nose systems with few sensor elements, resulting in constrained accuracy, poor generalizability, and limited robustness across diverse patient populations. Since *e*-nose functionality depends on cooperative sensor responses analogous to olfactory receptor networks, increasing the number of sensor elements is essential to capture a broader range of chemical signatures and improve both sensitivity and specificity for early detection and accurate stage identification.

A further knowledge gap concerns the potential interference of other gynecologic malignancies—particularly endometrial cancer (EC)—in OC detection. Misclassification of EC as OC could lead to inappropriate diagnostic procedures, suboptimal treatment, unnecessary patient's psychological distress, and increased healthcare costs. Addressing this challenge is critical to developing reliable diagnostic tools that can accurately distinguish OC from other gynecologic cancers.

To overcome these limitations, we extended our previous work by improving model interpretability, employing a more rigorous strategy to evaluate model robustness, and simulating clinically relevant diagnostic settings, such as differentiating OC from a combined group of EC cases and healthy controls.^[24,25] We employed a 32-element *e*-nose system to analyze blood plasma samples from 134 OC cases, 41 EC cases, and 115 healthy controls, representing a significantly larger and more heterogeneous dataset than those reported in previous studies. The extended sensor array enables broader capture of VOC signatures, enhancing the diversity of detectable metabolic patterns across populations, thereby improving model robustness and generalizability. Our approach combines this expanded sensing capability with a robust ML framework that integrates feature engineering for stage-specific VOC pattern recognition, ensemble learning

strategies, and sensor exclusion algorithms, resulting in improved diagnostic performance and generalizability, particularly for early-stage OC detection—a critical shortcoming of prior models. Rigorous validation procedures further accounted for potential EC-related confounding effects, ensuring diagnostic specificity.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Machine Learning Approaches for Early Detection of Ovarian Cancer in Healthy Population

We systematically evaluated 43 distinct models within MATLAB's Classification Learner application to identify the optimal ML architecture for early OC detection. Our analysis encompassed 85 distinctive features extracted from each signal corresponding to **Group 1** (G_1)—healthy individuals—and **Group 2** (G_2)—OC patients (detailed in the Experimental Section and Supporting Information). The comprehensive feature dataset included signals from all sensors and samples representing two distinct cohorts. For each model, we implemented a rigorous 90–10 train-test data partition protocol combined with a fivefold crossvalidation (CV) strategy. Comparative analysis of model performance evaluation is presented in Table S1, Supporting Information. Among all tested architectures, the Optimizable Ensemble model—featuring automated hyperparameter optimization and multiple decision trees—achieved the

best performance, with validation and test accuracies of 77.2% and 77.6%, surpassing all alternatives (Figure S1, Supporting Information). While this served as our baseline model, the moderate accuracy warranted further optimization through in-depth analysis of sensor response patterns and systematic evaluation of individual sensor and feature contributions.

To elucidate characteristic ϵ -nose response patterns, we generated a comprehensive multipanel visualization (Figure S2, Supporting Information) illustrating the spatiotemporal responses of the 32-element ϵ -nose to blood plasma VOCs from healthy individuals and OC patients during 600 s measurement intervals. Distinct response signatures were evident across all sensor signals for each sample category, exemplified by the representative patterns of sensor #10 in **Figure 1**. Notably, at least 50% of sensors exhibited saturation during the adsorption phase, indicating strong VOC interactions, while specific sensors displayed marked intergroup differences. Sensor #16 consistently produced weaker signals, resulting in a nearly uniform 2D distribution pattern.

To statistically validate these observations and evaluate sensor response reliability, we analyzed mean sensor signals with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for each sensor exposed to blood plasma VOCs from both cohorts (Figure S3a, Supporting Information). The varying CI widths surrounding the mean signals provided critical insights into data dispersion and signal stability: narrower CIs indicated more consistent responses and potentially greater discriminatory power between healthy and OC groups, whereas broader CIs reflected higher variability likely

Figure 1. Detailed spatiotemporal response of sensor #10 in the ϵ -nose to VOCs emitted from blood plasma samples, measured across two batches (108 healthy individuals and 88 OC patients). Normalized signal intensity (scale 0–1, color bar at the top) is shown for the healthy (left panel) and OC (right panel) groups, with time (s) on the y-axis and individual patient index on the x-axis. Horizontal white dashed lines indicate the experimental phases: baseline (0–20 s), sample introduction (20–40 s), adsorption (40–360 s), desorption (360–500 s), and recovery (500–600 s). More details on these phases are given in the Experimental Section. Note: the healthy individual and patient indices are not arranged in chronological order of sample collection or measurement; instead, they represent a simple sequential indexing of all samples in the dataset (from the combined signal database for sensor #10 across both batches).

arising from interpatient heterogeneity or sensor sensitivity fluctuations. These statistical metrics complemented the spatiotemporal patterns observed in Figure S2, Supporting Information, enabling a comprehensive assessment of *e*-nose performance characteristics. Several sensors demonstrated statistically significant differences between cohorts (Figure S3b, Supporting Information), identifying them as potential discriminatory elements in sample classification. We hypothesized that such sensors would exhibit lower similarity coefficients (sensor utility coefficients), as defined in the Experimental Section. Comparative visualization of these coefficients across the sensor array confirmed this expectation (Figure S4, Supporting Information)—sensors with distinct intergroup signal patterns consistently displayed lower similarity coefficients. This systematic evaluation identified sensor #17 and sensor #25 as minimally contributory to classification accuracy, exhibiting minimal intergroup signal differentiation and reduced variability (narrow 95% CI), see Figure S2, Supporting Information.

Building on these findings, we systematically evaluated the Optimizable Ensemble model across all 32 iterative cycles (Table S3 and Figure S5, Supporting Information). Beginning with the full sensor array (step 1), we progressively removed one sensor per iteration until only one remained (step 32). Notably, step 3 and step 4 achieved validation and test accuracies approaching or exceeding 95.0%. The models exhibited robust sensitivity and specificity values, indicating high discriminatory capabilities for both positive and negative classifications. Although the model at step 31 yielded a perfect score of 1 across all evaluation metrics at both validation and test levels, this likely reflected overfitting. We observed that signal variability diminishes substantially with decreasing dataset dimensionality. This reduction in data complexity typically results in artificially elevated accuracy metrics due to model overfitting, a phenomenon where models memorize training data patterns rather than developing generalizable feature recognition capabilities.^[36] Consequently, we selected the step 3 configuration (excluding sensor #17 and sensor #25) as the optimal model. This configuration achieved high validation and test accuracies (95.5% and 96.3%, respectively) with well-balanced sensitivity and specificity metrics, representing the most reliable framework for capturing intrinsic signal patterns while avoiding overfitting.

To further validate the robustness of the step 3 model, we assessed its performance under varying train-test data splitting using the reduced feature dataset. The main methodological difference from earlier analyses lay in the hyperparameter optimization strategy. We initially implemented comprehensive Bayesian optimization across all hyperparameters, facilitating an exhaustive exploration of the hyperparameter space. This methodology proved optimal for selecting sensor subsets, ensuring maximum model performance through precise parameter calibration. To assess robustness, we transitioned to automatic hyperparameter optimization, which is computationally efficient. We conducted 15 independent training and testing iterations. Given that the feature-observation matrix partitioning into train and test datasets and the fivefold CV assignments occur stochastically, a robust model should maintain consistent performance across runs regardless of data distribution. Any substantial performance variability would indicate compromised robustness. Our analysis confirmed that stochastic data partitioning had a

negligible impact on model metrics (Figure 2a). The classifier, developed using the optimal sensor subset, demonstrated stable performance, with a mean validation accuracy of 96.6% (95% CI: 96.5–96.8) and a mean test accuracy of 97.2% (95% CI: 96.9–97.4). Corresponding sensitivity values were 96.5% (95% CI: 96.4–96.6%) for validation and 97.1% (95% CI: 96.8–97.4), while specificity reached 96.8% (95% CI: 96.7–97.0) and 97.3% (95% CI: 96.8–97.8), respectively. The narrow CIs confirm the high classifier's stability and reliability.

Among the 15 trained and tested models, the top-performing configuration (selected by maximal test accuracy) achieved 96.7% (98.0%) validation (test) accuracy, 96.4% (97.6%) sensitivity, and 97.0% (98.5%) specificity. To elucidate the model's decision-making framework, we implemented MATLAB's *predictor Importance* function for feature importance analysis (Figure 2b). This investigation identified ten predominant features, with six directly associated with signal derivatives. Notably, Hjorth parameters—specifically *complexity* and *mobility*—emerged as crucial determinants of the model's predictive capabilities. Figure 2c–e illustrates violin plots displaying feature value distributions across healthy control and OC cohorts for the three most significant features. To determine whether the differences in feature values between two classes were statistically significant, we performed Wilcoxon rank-sum tests and calculated the corresponding *p*-values for each feature.^[37] These *p*-values measured the probability of observed intergroup differences occurring by chance. Notably, the first and third features exhibited *p*-values below 0.001 ($>3\sigma$ significance), while the second feature exhibited a *p*-value of 0.007. These findings show high statistical significance for the first and third features, and robust statistical significance for the second feature, confirming that these distinctions were unlikely to occur by chance. This additional evidence reinforces the importance of these features in distinguishing between healthy and OC samples. The heatmap visualizations in Figure 2f,g illustrate the variation in feature patterns between healthy control and OC groups across the ten most significant features. The Z-score normalized values are shown for all signals (model at step 3, comprising 30 signals per sample). Detailed analysis highlights distinct differences in feature patterns between the two groups.

Next, we analyzed the model's optimized hyperparameters, comprising Gentle Adaptive Boosting (*GentleBoost*) method, 495 learning cycles, a learning rate of 0.0094, and a minimum leaf size of 34. The *GentleBoost* algorithm employed here sequentially integrated 495 weak learners into the ensemble, iteratively refining previous model errors through a weighted average of predictions.^[38] Following hyperparameter optimization, we conducted additional robustness assessments using fixed hyperparameters to isolate the effect of random variations in training and test data distribution. Results demonstrated remarkable consistency with the optimized model, achieving validation (test) accuracy of 97.0% (98.2%), sensitivity of 96.5% (97.8%), and specificity of 97.5% (98.5%). These findings confirm the robustness of the selected hyperparameter configuration in maintaining consistent performance across varying data distributions.

Further validation using a 75–25 train-test partition demonstrated sustained performance of the classifier, with validation (test) accuracy of 96.1% (97.8%), sensitivity of 96.2% (97.5%), and specificity of 96.0% (98.1%). This result highlights the

Figure 2. a) Bar plot of mean performance metrics (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity) at validation and test levels with 95% CIs. b) Feature importance analysis of the top ten features ranked by importance score. c–e) Violin plots illustrating the distribution of the three most important features across the two classes considered, with corresponding p -values indicated within each plot. f–g) Heatmaps representing the variation in feature patterns between the healthy control and OC groups for the top ten features, with normalized Z-score values represented by the color scale.

classifier’s generalization capabilities across diverse data partitioning scenarios.

Feature importance analysis revealed seven features with zero importance scores among the 85 features evaluated, suggesting potential for model simplification through feature reduction without compromising performance. The streamlined 78-feature model achieved nearly identical performance metrics: validation (test) accuracy of 96.7% (97.9%), sensitivity of 96.5% (97.4%), and specificity of 97.0% (98.5%) under 90–10 train-test split scheme. These findings confirm that this model simplification does not affect the accuracy significantly while reducing computational complexity. Interestingly, the refined model’s optimized hyperparameters showed subtle variations: *GentleBoost* method, 499 learning cycles, 0.1787 learning rate, and minimum leaf size of 1, indicating a faster learning rate and smaller leaf sizes consistent with reduced dataset complexity and noise. These adaptations highlight the dynamic relationship between dataset composition and hyperparameter optimization in determining model training characteristics.

To further assess the model’s robustness, we implemented a 10-fold CV scheme in addition to the fivefold CV approach. Analysis of both CV schemes revealed that while the 10-fold CV scheme achieved a marginally higher mean validation accuracy (97.0%) compared to a fivefold CV scheme (96.6%), parameter variations remained within statistical error, indicating no significant performance difference. These results demonstrate consistent model performance across different validation frameworks, confirming strong reliability and generalizability. Comprehensive comparative statistics for all hyperparameters and performance

metrics are summarized in Table S4 and Table S5, Supporting Information.

The results obtained establish our methodology as a strong candidate among emerging OC diagnostic strategies. We benchmarked our research against the current state-of-the-art by comparing 34 studies conducted between 2024 and 2025 (Figure 3) employing diverse approaches, including ML models (e.g., logistic regression, fuzzy deep learning), liquid biopsy techniques (e.g., platelet RNA profiling, extracellular vesicles), imaging modalities (e.g., ultrasound, PET/CT), and biomarker panels combining CA125, HE4, and metabolomics.^[13–16,39–68] These studies reported variable sensitivity (0.22–1.00) and specificity (0.32–1.00), often requiring large cohorts (up to 328 201 participants) or complex data acquisition. In contrast, our method achieved high sensitivity (0.97) and specificity (0.97) with a moderate cohort size (134 OC cases among 249 participants), underscoring its clinical feasibility (Figure 3).

Notably, compared to previous work using near-infrared fluorescence detection using carbon nanotube arrays (sensitivity: 0.87, specificity: 0.98), our approach achieved higher sensitivity while maintaining comparable specificity.^[31] Performance also compares favorably with established clinical standards such as proteomic tests for CA125, HE4, and ultrasound, though their performance metrics vary widely by cohort composition and demographics.

The A1 model’s high performance was further corroborated by stable validation and test receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves with narrow 95% CIs for both classes (Figure 4a,b). Complementing these, Figure 4c,d displays the best validation

Figure 3. Scatter plot showing the relationship between sensitivity (x-axis) and specificity (y-axis) in OC detection across 34 studies employing various diagnostic methods, published between 2024 and 2025.^[13–16,39–68] The plot is divided into four subplots with axis breaks (sensitivity: 0.4–0.44; specificity: 0.6–0.65) to improve visual clarity. Filled circles denote studies with ≤1000 participants (marker size proportional to study population, range: 29–987; color represents case cohort size, range: 15–2756, from blue to red). Diamonds indicate larger studies with >1000 participants (range: 1101–328201), outlined in black. The present study, marked by a red asterisk (sensitivity: 0.97; specificity: 0.97), included 134 OC cases within a total cohort of 249 participants. Reference numbers correspond to marker colors, facilitating crossidentification.

Figure 4. a,b) Mean ROC curves with 95% CIs for validation and test datasets, showing near-perfect classification of healthy individuals and OC patients. Insets highlight specific curve segments to enhance CI visibility. c–f) Validation and test confusion matrices at both signal and patient levels.

and test confusion matrices from 15 iterations, further demonstrating the Optimizable Ensemble model's highest efficiency in discriminating between healthy individuals and OC patients.

The model demonstrated high performance at both validation and test levels, correctly classifying 97.0% (3013/3105) of signals from healthy individuals and 96.4% (3618/3753) from OC patients during validation, and 98.6% (340/345) from healthy individuals and 97.6% (407/417) from OC patients during testing.

Although these results reflect strong signal-level classification, our clinical objective was to achieve accurate patient-level diagnosis. To ensure that performance metrics truly reflected patient-level generalizability, we implemented a refined data splitting strategy with rigorous control on data splitting. Specifically, we executed a 9010 patient-level split, ensuring complete patient data separation between training and test datasets, coupled with a fivefold stratified CV. Subsequently, we trained and tested the ML model on the refined dataset, following step 3 methodology while excluding data from sensor #17 and sensor #25. After generating signal-level predictions, we employed a majority voting algorithm, aggregating predictions across 30 consecutive signals to derive patient-level predictions. This refined approach enabled patient-level predictions based on signal-level training, effectively mitigating data leakage between training and test datasets while maximizing utilization of all available signal data. The patient-level validation and test confusion matrices, illustrated in Figure 4e,f, demonstrated high classification accuracy across all samples, highlighting the model's enhanced discriminative capabilities at both signal and patient levels.

2.2. Classification of Ovarian Cancer Progression: Machine Learning Models for Stage Differentiation

Blood plasma samples analyzed in this study were collected from OC patients representing multiple stages of disease progression. The early detection of stage I is particularly critical, as it enables timely diagnosis and treatment, thereby significantly improving clinical outcomes, survival rates, and patients' quality of life.^[69] To address this, we developed an ML-based classifier designed to differentiate stage I OC from more advanced stages (II–IV). Following the same analytical framework established in Section 2.1, we focused on the G_2 cohort, subdivided into stage I ($n = 41$) and stage II–IV ($n = 93$) OC patient groups. Comparative signal analyses (Figure S6 and Figure S7, Supporting Information), together with similarity coefficient assessments (Figure S8, Supporting Information), revealed that sensor #17 and sensor #25 produced highly similar responses across both subgroups. We then applied the iterative sensor elimination protocol, generating a sequence of 32 sensor subsets (Table S6, Supporting Information). Notably, exclusion of sensor #17 and sensor #25 with high similarity coefficients did not affect model performance during the initial iterations (Table S7 and Figure S9, Supporting Information). The classifier maintained high accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity through step 15, achieving a peak test accuracy of 96.2%. This performance stability indicates strong model robustness despite progressive sensor elimination, i.e., reduction in sensor data. Beyond step 16, performance metrics declined sharply (train accuracy dropped to 62.7%, test accuracy to 65.1%), indicating loss of critical discriminatory information. Steps 27–31 exhibited artificially elevated performance, achieving validation and test accuracies of 100%,

consistent with overfitting due to the limited number of sensor inputs and sample size. Consequently, we selected the model at step 1 for further analysis, as it demonstrated consistently strong performance (96.1% test accuracy) and balanced sensitivity and specificity.

To assess model robustness, we performed 15 independent train-test cycles using the full dataset. The results showed a mean validation accuracy of 93.2% (95% CI: 93.0–93.3) and a mean test accuracy of 92.8% (95% CI: 92.1–93.5), confirming consistent performance across iterations. Sensitivity was high, with mean validation and test values of 96.4% (95% CI: 96.3–96.6) and 96.3% (95% CI: 95.8–96.9). Specificity was moderately lower, with mean validation and test values of 85.7% (95% CI: 85.5–86.0) and 84.8% (95% CI: 83.1–86.6).

To refine the classifier’s performance in differentiating OC stages, we explored multiple alternative classification schemes (Table S8 and Table S9, Supporting Information). Table S8, Supporting Information outlines model configurations, including train-test splits, CV strategies, and hyperparameter optimization settings, while Table S9, Supporting Information summarizes performance metrics for seven distinct models. Our analysis showed that variations in train-test split schemes (90–10 vs. 75–25) and CV settings (5-fold vs. 10-fold) had minimal influence on classification accuracy, which remained consistently high across all models (94.5–95.6%). Based on its competitive performance and balanced data structure, we selected the model trained using a 90–10 split scheme and fivefold CV for further evaluation. The optimized hyperparameters for this model employed the *GenileBoost* method with 499 learning cycles, a learning rate of 0.1893, and a minimum leaf size of 2.

Feature importance analysis applied to this model showed that the four most important features—*max1stDeriv*, *SNR*, *complexity*, *max2ndDeriv*—each contributed less than 7.0% to the overall classification outcome (Figure S10a, Supporting Information). This finding highlights the need to preserve a broad feature set to ensure robust model performance. Interestingly, while *max1stDeriv* emerged as the most important feature, its *p*-value of 0.562 (Figure S10b, Supporting Information) indicated no statistically significant difference between groups despite its high utility in model decision-making. Conversely, other features showed statistically significant intergroup differences, reinforcing their relevance in OC stage discrimination (Figure S10c,d, Supporting Information).

Further insight into the model’s behavior was obtained through heatmap visualizations (Figure S10e,f, Supporting Information), which displayed Z-score normalized values of the 10 most significant features for all 32 signals across samples. Distinct feature distribution patterns were evident between stage I and stages II–IV, confirming the model’s ability to distinguish between early and advanced OC stages. Complementary validation using ROC curves (Figure 5a,b) and confusion matrices (Figure 5c–f) further verified strong classification performance at both the signal and patient levels.

From a practical standpoint, classifier B1, trained for early-stage OC detection, can be functionally integrated with classifier A1 (Section 2.1), which differentiates OC patients from healthy controls. In this sequential diagnostic workflow, classifier A1 would first identify the presence of OC, after which classifier B1 would determine disease stage. To explore broader screening applications, we also developed a parallel classifier distinguishing

Figure 5. a, b) Mean ROC curves with 95% CIs for validation and test datasets, showing robust classification between stage I and stages II–IV OC patients. c–f) Validation and test confusion matrices at both signal and patient levels, confirming the Optimizable Ensemble model’s superior performance in accurately distinguishing early- from advanced-stage OC.

stage I OC from a combined group of stages II–IV and healthy controls. This model holds potential for large-scale screening, where early detection is critical for effective intervention and improved clinical outcomes. Although this model achieved high accuracy and specificity (Figure S11, Supporting Information), its sensitivity plateaued at $\approx 76.0\%$ (step 5) and did not improve with additional sensor elimination. These findings support the feasibility and clinical relevance of the sequential A1 \rightarrow B1 classification strategy, while indicating that further methodological innovations may be required to enhance sensitivity in early-stage detection.

2.3. Differential Diagnosis Through Machine Learning: Ovarian Versus Endometrial Cancer Classification

Building on the success of the classifiers developed for distinguishing healthy individuals from OC patients and for identifying cancer stages, we further extended our investigation to include EC. Blood plasma samples from 41 EC patients were collected and analyzed to develop a model capable of differentiating between OC and EC. This advancement underscores the ϵ -nose system's ability to generate distinct response patterns for different cancer types, highlighting its potential for cancer-specific detection.

We selected EC for comparison with OC due to the anatomical proximity of the uterus and ovaries within the female reproductive system. This spatial relationship may lead to overlapping biomarker signatures in blood plasma, making accurate differentiation both challenging and clinically essential. Reliable distinction between these malignancies is particularly valuable in cases where initial symptoms or imaging results are inconclusive, potentially enabling earlier and more accurate diagnosis. The need for such discriminative capability is reinforced by limitations of conventional methods, including DNA profiling. Notably, prior studies have demonstrated that EC and OC cell lines may be misclassified as other cancer cell lines based solely on genetic analysis.^[70] These findings highlight the diagnostic complexity of gynecologic malignancies and the need for complementary technologies such as VOC-based sensing.

Following our established methodology, we constructed multi-panel visualizations to compare sensor responses to blood plasma samples from OC and EC patients (Figure S12 and Figure S13, Supporting Information). In contrast to OC stage differentiation, we observed that a substantially greater number of sensors displayed marked differences in both signal amplitude and shape. Consistent with previous analyses, sensor #17 and sensor #25 exhibited the highest similarity coefficients (Figure S14, Supporting Information). Based on the sensor elimination procedure (Table S10, Supporting Information), these sensors were excluded at step 3 of the optimization process. The model corresponding to step 3 was selected as optimal, as it provided the best overall balance across key performance parameters relative to other steps. Although models generated up to step 10 also yielded acceptable results (Table S11 and Figure S15, Supporting Information), concerns about potential overfitting at later steps led us to prioritize early-stage configurations as more reliable.

To assess model robustness, we conducted 15 independent training-testing cycles. The mean validation accuracy was 96.3% (95% CI: 96.2–96.4), with a slightly higher mean test

accuracy of 97.1% (95% CI: 96.7–97.4). The model achieved high sensitivity, with mean validation and test sensitivities of 98.2% (95% CI: 98.1–98.2) and 98.3% (95% CI: 97.9–98.6). Mean validation specificity was 90.3% (95% CI: 90.0–90.5) and mean test specificity was 93.2% (95% CI: 91.5–94.8). These results underscore the classifier's high and consistent performance in distinguishing between EC and OC. The narrow CIs across all metrics indicate low interiteration variability, confirming model reliability and robustness. The model's stability was further confirmed by the narrow CIs observed in the ROC curves for both classes (Figure 6a,b). At the patient level, confusion matrices demonstrated perfect classification of cancer types, outperforming signal-level results (Figure 6c–f). This improvement is attributed to the majority-voting strategy applied across the remaining 30 sensors, which effectively reduced the influence of individual sensor noise and variability.

All models discussed in this section were developed using a 90–10 split scheme and fivefold CV. To further investigate the influence of training configuration on model performance, we evaluated alternative setups (Table S12 and Table S13, Supporting Information). Comparisons across different classifiers revealed that both the train-test data split ratio and hyperparameter optimization may impact model performance. Models trained using a 90–10 split (C1–C5) generally achieved higher accuracy and area under ROC curve (AUC) values than those trained using a 75–25 split (C6, C7), indicating that larger training sets enhanced generalization. Furthermore, classifiers employing hyperparameter optimization (C1, C2, C5–C7) consistently outperformed nonoptimized counterparts (C3, C4), emphasizing the importance of fine-tuning parameters such as learning cycles, learning rate, and minimum leaf size. Among these, classifier C5—combining feature exclusion with hyperparameter optimization—provided the best balance between accuracy and feature selection efficiency. These findings underscore the importance of rigorous training strategies design and fine-tuning to improve model reliability and predictive power.

Feature importance analysis identified signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) as the most impactful feature, followed by four derivative-based parameters: *max2ndDeriv*, *max1stDeriv*, *complexity*, and *mobility* (Figure S16a, Supporting Information). Violin plots and corresponding statistical analysis yielded *p*-values below 0.001 for the three most influential features (Figure S16b–d, Supporting Information), confirming strong statistical discrimination between OC and EC samples. This result suggests that these features capture key biological differences between the two malignancies. Heatmap visualizations of the ten most important features further revealed clear separation between OC and EC sample patterns, corroborating the model's classification capabilities (Figure S16e,f, Supporting Information). Optimized hyperparameters for classifier C1—employing the *GentleBoost* method, 320 learning cycles, a 0.9950 learning rate, and a minimum leaf size of 1—were instrumental in achieving the high predictive performance observed.

To approximate a more realistic diagnostic scenario, we expanded the EC group to include healthy controls and OC patients at stages II–IV. We then assessed the model's ability to i) distinguish OC from this composite EC + healthy control group and ii) discriminate stage I OC from a combined population of stages II–IV OC, EC, and healthy controls. These

Figure 6. a,b) Mean ROC curves with 95% CIs for validation and test datasets, showing robust classification between EC and OC patients. c–f) Validation and test confusion matrices at both signal and patient levels, confirming the Optimizable Ensemble model’s superior performance in accurately distinguishing between EC and OC patients.

scenarios more closely simulate real-world screening contexts, where early-stage OC must be identified within heterogeneous populations potentially affected by multiple or overlapping pathologies. Despite sequential sensor elimination, model sensitivity did not exceed 80.0% for these extended tasks, although specificity remained consistently high (Figure S17 and Figure S18, Supporting Information). These results indicate that while the models reliably identify noncancerous (true negative) cases, further refinement is needed to improve early-stage (true positive) detection in complex diagnostic conditions.

To address this limitation, we grouped OC and EC cases into a single “composite cancer” class and compared them to healthy controls. Evaluation of this OE-H (ovarian-endometrial vs. healthy) revised model yielded sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy values of 93.0% at step 2, with all metrics improving to 96.0% by step 6 (Figure S19, Supporting Information). This composite classifier holds potential for clinical screening workflows. Integrated with classifiers such as C1 and B1, it could first detect a general cancerous condition, then determine the specific cancer type (OC or EC), and finally differentiate between stage I and more advanced OC stages. This hierarchical classification framework offers a streamlined and efficient diagnostic pipeline, enabling early detection, accurate cancer-type classification, and efficient clinical decision-making with strong translational potential.

3. Conclusion

This study presents a reliable and biomarker-independent approach for the detection of OC based on blood plasma analysis.

Our method classifies sensor responses from an ϵ -nose exposed to the full spectrum of VOCs emitted by 1 mL blood plasma samples from healthy individuals and OC patients. We developed a robust Optimizable Ensemble ML model, leveraging 85 time-domain, frequency-domain, and statistical features, along with similarity coefficients of individual sensors. This model achieved $\approx 97.0\%$ sensitivity and specificity in discriminating sensor signals corresponding to healthy controls versus OC patients. Crucially, the implementation of a majority-vote decision algorithm enabled perfect patient-level classification accuracy, highlighting the clinical relevance of our approach. Feature importance analysis, supported by Wilcoxon rank-sum testing, identified key contributors to model performance, demonstrating strong discriminatory power across datasets. The versatility of the approach was further validated through additional classification tasks, including OC staging and discrimination between OC and EC, resulting in the development of additional high-performance Optimizable Ensemble ML models.

Overall, this research represents a significant advance toward reliable, accessible, and minimally invasive VOC-based oncology diagnostics, with substantial translational potential for both clinical and population-level screening applications. By enabling early OC detection and timely intervention, it provides a viable strategy to improve clinical and patient outcomes and support more effective, precision-driven healthcare.

4. Experimental Section

Sample and Measurement Protocol: Blood plasma samples from healthy volunteers (aged 30–60 years) were collected at Linköping University

Hospital (Region Östergötland, Sweden), following written informed consent from all participating subjects in accordance with Swedish legislation. Preoperative peripheral blood plasma samples were obtained from patients diagnosed with epithelial borderline ovarian tumors and OC (aged 18–89), and EC (aged 41–90). OC samples were collected at Karolinska University Hospital (Stockholm, Sweden) between 2019 and 2020 and Lund University Hospital (Region Skåne, Sweden) between 2016 and 2020, while EC samples were collected at Lund University Hospital between 2015 and 2022. All samples were prepared in aliquots of 1 mL blood plasma and stored in biobanks in tubes frozen at $-80\text{ °C} \pm 1\text{ °C}$ until analysis. To preserve sample integrity, identical storage and handling procedures were followed, and each aliquot was thawed once only, immediately prior to VOC measurement at ambient temperature ($+21\text{ °C} \pm 1\text{ °C}$). Detailed protocols for the proper storage and handling of biological samples are available elsewhere.^[23] Appropriate Ethical Committee approval was obtained from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority in accordance with ethical review legislation, including Karolinska University Hospital, Faculty of Medicine, Reg. No. 2019-02140, and amendments from Lund University, Department of Medicine, Reg. No. 2022-03015-02 and Reg. No. 2023-01881-01.

e-Nose and Experimental Setup: All samples were measured utilizing an e-nose prototype developed by VOC Diagnostics AB (Linköping, Sweden).^[71] The system features a 32-element array of commercially available MOS gas sensors (Figaro TGS2X series), including TGS2602, TGS2603, TGS2620, TGS2611E, TGS2600, TGS2611C, TGS2444, and TGS2610. Sensor specifications are provided in Table S14, Supporting Information, while a photograph of the instrument can be found in Horvath et al.^[72] The sensors are organized into four banks of eight sensors each, operating at distinct temperatures. For each measurement, 1 mL of blood plasma was placed in a dedicated sample chamber maintained at ambient temperature ($+21\text{ °C} \pm 1\text{ °C}$), which was then positioned inside the e-nose tunnel. Data were recorded continuously at a sampling rate of 600 points/min over 10 min protocol. The procedure began with 20 s of baseline recording (0–20 s), followed by sample insertion at 20 s. After an additional 20 s, the system activated a fan at the tunnel exit (40 s) to draw VOCs released from the sample through the sensor array. The sample was removed from the chamber at 360 s, the fan continued to operate until 500 s, with the entire measurement lasting 600 s (Figure 7). This protocol allowed us to observe the full sensor response during and after VOC exposure. While the sample was inside the chamber, the sensors reacted to the volatiles emitted from the blood plasma. Continuing measurement after sample removal enabled monitoring of sensor recovery and relaxation, providing valuable insights into the physical and

chemical processes involved, including signal decay as chemical compounds dissipated and sensors returned to baseline.

Statistical Analysis and Machine Learning Framework: Prior to developing ML models for differentiating between healthy individuals and cancer patients' blood plasma samples, we implemented an algorithmic approach to evaluate the discriminatory efficacy of each of the 32 sensors. This analytical process facilitated the exclusion of sensor data exhibiting minimal discriminatory power. The following section delineates the methodological framework, beginning with the construction of the signal dataset. This comprehensive dataset encompasses sensor signals from two distinct cohorts: i) **Group 1 (G₁):** Healthy individuals, encompassing 115 unique signal sets (F_i) and ii) **Group 2 (G₂):** OC patients, encompassing 134 unique signal sets (F_j).

Each set $F_i \in G_1$ or $F_j \in G_2$ constitutes a matrix with dimensions 6000×32 , wherein the 32 columns correspond to individual sensors, each generating a unique voltage signal, while the 6000 rows represent temporal measurements, reflecting the signal acquisition duration. To ensure consistency and enhance signal quality (noise reduction), we implemented normalization and smoothing protocols for each set. Individual columns of the matrix (representing distinct sensors) underwent normalization to the [0, 1] range, ensuring cross-signal comparability irrespective of scale variations. This normalization transformation was executed for each sensor s of F_i (or F_j) using

$$F'_{i,s} = \frac{F_{i,s} - \min(F_{i,s})}{\max(F_{i,s}) - \min(F_{i,s})} \quad (1)$$

where $\min(F_{i,s})$ and $\max(F_{i,s})$ denote the minimum and maximum sensor readings in column s . Subsequently, a Savitzky–Golay filter (polynomial order of 2 and smoothing factor of 0.25) was applied to each normalized column utilizing MATLAB's *smoothdata* function (note: MATLAB automatically computes the window size via a heuristic linked to this smoothing factor), yielding optimized smoothed signal F''_i (or F''_j).^[73,74]

$$F''_i = \text{smoothdata}(F'_i, \text{"sgolay"}) \quad (2)$$

Following preprocessing, we employed Pearson correlation coefficient analysis to quantify the signal similarity between healthy (**Group 1**) and OC (**Group 2**) cohorts. For each sensor $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, 32\}$, we extracted corresponding signals from pre-processed sets F''_i for **Group 1** and F''_j for **Group 2**. For subject i from **Group 1**, the sensor s signal was represented by the vector $F''_i(:, s)$, where $F''_i \in G_1$. For subject j from **Group 2**, the

Figure 7. Time-series response of sensor #1 from the e-nose during analysis of blood plasma from a 63-year-old female patient diagnosed with ovarian mucinous adenocarcinoma. The measurement comprises five phases: baseline (0–20 s, light gray), sample introduction (20–40 s, light blue), adsorption (40–360 s, blue), desorption (360–500 s, orange), and recovery (500–600 s, light green). The black line indicates the normalized sensor signal.

sensor s signal was represented by the vector $F_j''(\cdot, s)$, where $F_j'' \in G_2$. The Pearson correlation coefficient $\rho_{s,ij}$ between signals for sensor s from subject $i \in G_1$ and subject $j \in G_2$ was computed as

$$\rho_{s,ij} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{6000} (F_i''(k, s) - \overline{F_i''(\cdot, s)}) (F_j''(k, s) - \overline{F_j''(\cdot, s)})}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^{6000} (F_i''(k, s) - \overline{F_i''(\cdot, s)})^2 \sum_{k=1}^{6000} (F_j''(k, s) - \overline{F_j''(\cdot, s)})^2}} \quad (3)$$

where $F_i''(k, s)$ and $F_j''(k, s)$ represent the k -th values of the signals for sensor s from subjects $i \in G_1$ and $j \in G_2$. $\overline{F_i''(\cdot, s)}$ and $\overline{F_j''(\cdot, s)}$ denote the mean values of the signals from sensor s for subjects i and j . This correlation analysis was performed exhaustively across all possible subject pairs from **Group 1** and **Group 2** for each sensor. For a given sensor S , following the computation of Pearson correlation coefficients $\rho_{s,ij}$ between each subject pair $i \in G_1$ and $j \in G_2$, the mean similarity coefficient \overline{C}_s was calculated as

$$\overline{C}_s = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{|G_1|} \sum_{j=1}^{|G_2|} \rho_{s,ij}}{|G_1| \times |G_2|} \quad (4)$$

where $|G_1|$ and $|G_2|$ represent the number of subjects (signal sets) in **Group 1** and **Group 2**. This similarity coefficient \overline{C}_s effectively quantifies the average correlation between signals from healthy individuals and cancer patients for each sensor.

We developed an iterative optimization protocol for sensor selection by systematically eliminating sensors with the least discriminatory power. The process commenced with the complete sensor array, calculating similarity coefficients (\overline{C}_s) for each sensor. During each iteration, the sensor exhibiting the highest similarity coefficient—indicating minimal differentiation capacity between healthy individuals and OC patients—was identified as noninformative and removed from the dataset. After removing the least useful sensor, similarity coefficients were recalculated for the remaining sensors. This iterative procedure continued for 32 cycles, with one sensor excluded per cycle until a single sensor remained. The optimization process generated a comprehensive list of remaining sensors after each iteration (Table S15, Supporting Information). It is important to note that this list was generated by applying sample-wise range normalization and the Savitzky–Golay filter (polynomial order of 2, smoothing factor of 0.25) to the raw sensor signals prior to calculating similarity coefficients. In principle, sample-wise range normalization could have been even omitted, since the Pearson correlation is invariant to linear scaling and centering. However, we included it in the analysis to ensure numerical stability of the calculations and comparability of the data between samples, as well as to guarantee the correctness of subsequent analysis steps that are sensitive to scaling. Figure S20, Supporting Information presents a comparative analysis of similarity coefficients calculated using different normalization approaches: sample-wise, class-wise, and global normalization. It is evident that the coefficients remain consistent across all methods, with sensors #17 and #25 consistently identified as the least useful. This indicates that the relative performance ranking of sensors is robust and independent of the chosen normalization strategy. Furthermore, we examined the impact of normalization type (none, z-score, or min–max range) and smoothing factor (0.1, 0.25, or 0.5) on the similarity coefficients (Figure S21a–d, Supporting Information), revealing that normalization has no discernible effect on their values. In contrast, the smoothing factor exerted only minimal influence, without altering the overarching trend that sensors #17 and #25 offer the lowest utility in distinguishing between classes. Additionally, we consider a smoothing factor of 0.25 to be the optimal choice for preprocessing the sensor signals in our dataset. This is because signals processed with a factor of 0.1 remained excessively noisy, whereas a factor of 0.5 produced no meaningful improvements relative to 0.25, as demonstrated by representative signals from sensors #1 and #2 of a randomly selected sample (Figure S22, Supporting Information).

The subsequent analytical phase involved feature matrix construction, which, combined with the label vector, facilitated the creation of training and test datasets for ML model development. Features were extracted

from signals grouped by class and pre-processed with class-wise range normalization and Savitzky–Golay smoothing (polynomial order of 2, smoothing factor of 0.25). We did not apply global normalization in this case because it would pool signals across classes, potentially introducing artifacts that dilute class-specific variability. In addition, we extracted a subset of features directly from the raw signals, without any normalization or smoothing, to serve as a baseline for comparison and to isolate the effects of preprocessing on model performance. The feature extraction process yielded 85 distinct features, encompassing time-domain, frequency-domain, and statistical parameters derived from raw signals, smoothed-normalized signals, and their derivatives (Table 1). A detailed feature characterization is provided in Table S16, Supporting Information. This extensive feature extraction methodology ensured comprehensive signal characterization across temporal and frequency domains, providing ML algorithms with robust pattern recognition capabilities.

Figure 8 illustrates the overall workflow employed in this study. The process begins with the preparation of the initial feature dataset, which is generated by extracting 85 features from each sensor signal, followed by model selection. For ML model selection, we systematically evaluated 43 distinct classifiers available within MATLAB's Classification Learner application using a 90–10 train-test split, fivefold CV, and default training parameters, selecting the method with the highest crossvalidated and test performance based on accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity metrics.

If the selected model achieved sufficiently high performance, it was designated as the final model and subjected to further analyses to assess its stability and patient-level predictive capability. Conversely, if the model trained on the complete dataset exhibited suboptimal performance, an optimization strategy was implemented to refine the initial feature dataset by excluding data from sensors with low discriminatory power. At this stage, we calculated similarity coefficients for all sensors and ranked them based on their utility (note: these coefficients were computed exclusively during this optimization phase). To determine the optimal sensor configuration for classification tasks, we integrated the initial feature dataset with an iterative evaluation procedure in which data were sequentially excluded from one or more sensors at each stage. For each configuration, the resulting feature dataset was divided into training and test subsets (90–10 split), followed by model training, fivefold CV, and testing. At the first stage, data from all sensors were included in the feature dataset. At subsequent stages, data from one sensor were excluded at a time, and the updated dataset was again split (90–10) and used for model training, validation, and testing. Across all 32 resulting models, we identified the sensor configuration that provided the best balance between accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity, which was then adopted to construct a refined feature dataset corresponding to the optimal sensor subset.

After establishing the optimal sensor configuration, we performed a series of seven comparative experiments to examine the influence of

Table 1. Extracted features.

Feature Category	Features
Statistical	Root mean square (RMS), mean, median, standard deviation (Std), skewness, kurtosis, minimum, maximum, interquartile range (IQR), mean absolute deviation (MAD), harmonic mean, entropy, shape factor, impulse factor, crest factor, clearance factor
Time-domain	Zero-crossing rate, peak count, slope, time of minimum response (t_{\min}), time of maximum response (t_{\max}), Hjorth parameters (activity, mobility, complexity), peak-to-peak (PtP), signal-to-noise and distortion ratio (SINAD), total harmonic distortion (THD), signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), area under signal, signal energy, autocorrelation, maximum first derivative, maximum second derivative
Frequency-domain	Band power, peak amplitude, peak location, mean frequency, median frequency, occupied bandwidth, power bandwidth

Figure 8. Schematic overview of the workflow employed in this study.

various training parameters. Using the reduced feature dataset (excluding the least informative sensors), we systematically varied the train-test split ratio (90%–10% and 75%–25%), the number of CV folds (5 or 10), and the presence or absence of hyperparameter optimization. In one experimental scenario, we also assessed the impact of preliminary feature exclusion using a 90%–10% split and fivefold CV.

The finalized feature dataset—built using the optimal sensor configuration—was then employed for a robustness test, in which we repeated the 90%–10% train-test splitting procedure over 15 random cycles to verify whether classifier performance characteristics depended on the randomness of data partitioning.

To ensure fair evaluation, the feature dataset was further split at the patient level into 90% training and 10% held-out test patients. We then recalculated utility coefficients using only the training data, confirming that their values and sensor utility rankings were consistent with those derived from the full dataset (Figure S23, Supporting Information). Consequently, we excluded the data from sensors #17 and sensor #25 from both the training and test subsets. Model training, hyperparameter optimization and fivefold stratified CV were performed exclusively within the training set. The test set remained completely unseen until final evaluation, ensuring that model selection and optimization were fully independent of test data. No information from held-out patients was used in model selection or training.

The complete experimental workflow, encompassing data preprocessing, model development and training, and analytical procedures, was implemented using MATLAB R2024a environment,^[75] leveraging its advanced computational capabilities for ML applications.^[76,77]

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

blood plasma analysis, early diagnosis, electronic nose, machine learning diagnostics, noninvasive medical device, ovarian cancer detection, volatile organic compounds

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